

DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS APPLIED TO LOW POWER ONBOARD IMAGE COMPRESSION

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INTRODUCTION

New generations of earth observation satellites are equipped with better and higher quality sensors which allow higher resolution images to be captured. While the resulting captured images provide much more detail and information, they come with an increase in data size that can result in significant data transmission costs. Given the limited data rate in the downlink, sending all these high resolution data down to ground might take hours or even days. There has been extensive studies of efficient lossless compression to reduce the data size and therefore shorten the downlink time. However, these type of data compression techniques cannot cope with the increasing amount of sensor data produced in the Spacecraft. Lossy compression, within a certain threshold of quality, could be used to send to ground preliminary information from the sensor data in order to discern if the full data might be relevant and needed for the application at hand.

Recent research in the use of Artificial Intelligence and Deep Neural Networks for data compression have opened up new applications where these techniques have shown to perform as well as, if not better, than standard domain-specific compression algorithms. While neural networks have been studied for image compression since the 1980s [1], recent advances in hardware have allowed researchers to experiment with deep neural networks.

Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) with learned compression have shown to outperform state-of-the-art approaches by 2x when comparing bitrates of compressed images of equivalent quality. GANs are composed of a generative network - whose objective is to generate new data similar to training data - and a discriminative network - which evaluates this generated data with respect to training data. GAN based compression networks include an encoder stage that converts input data to latent space, which then serves as the input to the generative component (decoder) to recreate the original image.

The convolutional and deconvolutional layers in GAN networks can result in heavy use of computational resources. However the encoder and decoder stages of these neural networks can be decoupled to perform compression and decompression separately. In this paper, we propose to use these GAN based compression networks for on-board image compression for running only the encoder stage on the on-board computers, while the decoder can be run on ground stations to recreate the original images. We first provide a short introduction to typical neural data compression models and choose one such model to be tested with Klepsydra's AI inference engine.

Previous work using Klepsydra's AI inference engine has shown that significant performance gains can be obtained when running DNNs using Klepsydra AI's pipelining architecture. The convolutional layer architecture of the compression encoders allows us to implement the same pipelining strategies outlined in our previous works. As part of our research work, we have tested state-of-the-art compression algorithms with synthetic Space Data on space qualified hardware and evaluate the performance metrics - CPU usage, latency, and throughput - using Klepsydra AI inference engine for running these networks. We show that the CPU and power requirements when running compression networks with Klepsydra AI can be low enough to allow existing space systems to use on-board image compression using neural networks.

NEURAL DATA COMPRESSION

Background

Compression aims to represent data with as few bits as possible and with lossy compression the aim is to minimise the error between the original data and the representation reconstructed from the compressed bits. Lossless compression uses an *entropy coding* to encode discrete data into a compressed message. In case of lossy compression, the original data is

Figure 1: Image 1, original and reconstructions from compressed data

first encoded to a discrete set and this data is compressed using the *entropy coding*. The flexibility offered by allowing imperfect reconstruction of data allows the encoder to represent the original data with a smaller set. A focused review of traditional image compression for on-board satellites is presented in [2], and it proposes an architecture for on-board image compression for earth observation. The reader is referred to [3] for a deeper background into compression, including an introduction to neural data compression.

Learned Transform Coding

In neural data compression, the encoder uses transform coding - where the data is first decorrelated by converting to a transformed space - using neural networks. This transformed data is then quantized to obtain a discretized representation, which is then entropy coded to get a compressed output. During end-to-end training with Neural Data Compression, the encoder, decoder and the entropy model are considered together. The resulting AI model, trained to be able to reconstruct original images, is quite large.

As discussed in [4], while the encoder and decoder stages must be trained together and must share the entropy coding, the actual compression and decompression stages can be executed separately. This is demonstrated in the work presented in [5] where the objective is to compress images of size 28 x 28 pixels. The encoder in this case uses 2 convolutional layers and 2 dense layers. The decoder for the full model has equivalent "inverse" layers - 2 dense and 2 transposed convolutional layer. The full model for compressing has 2,554,641 trainable parameters, with only half of these parameters necessary for the compression step. In the context of on board compression, the network we need to run is thus a simple sequential network with convolutional and fully connected layers which is less than half the size of the fully trained model.

The network presented in [5] is quite rudimentary and cannot be used for efficiently compressing real images without too much loss of information. However, it informs our approach in separating the encoder stage and testing it for on-board use. In the following sections we discuss compression performance of different pretrained networks on images obtained from the Sentinel 2 mission.

Compression Performance on Sentinel Images

In order to evaluate the performance of prior work on earth observation data, we refer to publicly available deep neural compression networks [6] which were trained on generic image datasets. As such, the pretrained networks were optimised without constraints relating to network size, training complexity or computational complexity. The pretrained networks discussed in [7, 8, 9] allow choosing different quality levels where larger numbers imply higher quality and higher bit rates. We tested multiple quality levels of these networks on a small sample of images from Sentinel 2 dataset. The Table 1 shows the compressed sizes of various images with the different compression models.

The compressed data for these images was then decompressed on a separate computer, to obtain reconstructed images. We provide sample reconstructions for Image 1 and Image 7 in Fig 1 and Fig 2.

Table 1: Images sizes (in Kb) compressed with different models. b2018 refers to model in [9], bmsbj2018 refers to model in [7] and ms2020 refers to [8]. The numbered suffixes refer to quality levels

Model	Image1	Image2	Image3	Image4	Image5	Image6	Image7	Image8	Image9
Original	5903	1917	10097	2688	5186	4335	6084	3923	2640
b2018-1	68	360	229	30	57	543	63	48	36
bmsbj2018-1	67	272	261	24	55	363	65	44	32
bmsbj2018-2	117	382	490	38	105	625	124	77	52
bmsbj2018-3	194	534	872	65	180	955	225	128	81
bmsbj2018-4	290	720	1393	117	261	1329	328	193	124
bmsbj2018-5	471	1037	2270	212	445	2249	575	334	200
bmsbj2018-6	726	1440	3591	415	678	3136	882	528	310
bmsbj2018-7	1106	2074	5346	722	1005	4311	1256	799	489
ms2020-1	77	147	339	12	66	331	75	49	29
ms2020-2	147	272	717	34	138	652	159	97	60
ms2020-3	232	422	1192	74	218	1025	260	154	99
ms2020-4	356	693	1898	158	332	1674	399	245	166
ms2020-5	529	1118	2882	257	499	2543	608	372	261
ms2020-6	792	1844	4403	413	766	3794	920	575	416
ms2020-7	1176	2668	6292	707	1096	5157	1336	857	641
ms2020-8	1606	4089	8326	1029	1422	7038	1773	1191	945
ms2020-9	2052	5646	10429	1345	1757	9192	2262	1533	1269

(a) Original (b) Compressed with bmsbj2018-1 (c) Compressed with b2018

Figure 2: Image 7, original and reconstructions from compressed data

The compressed data is approximately 100x smaller than the original images in case of models used in Fig. 1 and 2. However, the reconstructed images do not show significant artefacts. Additionally, the pretrained models in this case are quite small - 16Mb for model b2018 [9] and 20 Mb for model bmsbj2018-1 [7]. In this case, we chose the lowest quality level of the trained model to demonstrate that for the purposes of earth observation data, the lowest quality provides an acceptable quality of image. Higher quality levels would give us reconstructed images with fewer compression artefacts at the cost of higher CPU and RAM usage.

Encoder Separation

We consider the model given in [7] with the lowest quality level for our work. The end-to-end network as described in the paper is shown in Fig. 3. The block labelled g_a represents the analysis transform and the block labelled h_a represents the hyperprior which is used to convey side information of the image. For the encoder, the data obtained from these two blocks is quantized before being encoded by the entropy coding. The entropy coding of the hyperprior is used in the compression step of the quantized image data represented by \hat{y} .

The python library [6] used for training the network and for compressing and decompressing images, implements the entropy coding and decoding (denoted by AE and AD in Fig. 3 respectively) as customised operators in C++. The remaining layers of the network can be represented by standard layers of deep learning frameworks - namely convolutional and transposed convolutional layers with appropriate padding, kernels, and strides for up-sampling/down-sampling.

Our objective here is to extract these convolutional and transposed convolution layers of the analysis stage for evaluation.

Figure 3: Neural Data compression network with hyperprior model [7]

For the purposes of benchmarking, we create a functionally equivalent network with the same architecture, but without the quantisation and entropy encoding stages. While this equivalent network is not trained on real data, it has the same number of parameters and thus will perform the same calculations when fed with real image data.

The equivalent network is 28Mb in size which is larger than the full network even though the full network includes the encoding and decoding stages. This is because the parameters of the convolutional layers of the full network are stored in the Fourier domain for maximum compressibility of the network [10]. Our goal in this work is to evaluate CPU usage of running the AI network without dealing with the compressibility of the network itself, and so we do not convert the parameters of the layers in the network.

Before discussing the performance of the equivalent network, we first give a background of Klepsydra AI in the next section.

KLEPSYDRA AI

Inference In Artificial Intelligence

There are several components to artificial intelligence (4). First, there is the training and design of the model. This activity is usually carried out by data scientists for a specific field of interest. Once the model is designed and trained, the model is deployed to the target computer for real-time execution. This is what is called inference. Inference consists of two parts, the trained model and the AI inference engine to execute the model. The focus of this research has been solely on the inference engine software algorithms.

Figure 4: AI main components

Trends In Artificial Intelligence Inference Acceleration

The most common operation in AI inference by far is matrix multiplications. These operations are constantly repeated for each input data to the AI model. In recent years, there has been a substantial development in this area with both industry and academia progressing steadily in this field. While the current trend is to focus on hardware acceleration like Graphic Processing Units (GPU) [8421507] and Field-programmable gate array (FPGA) [8594633], these techniques are currently not broadly available to the Space industry due to radiation issues and excessive energy consumption for the former, and programming costs for the latter. The use of CPU for inference, however, has been also undergoing an important evolution taking advantage of modern Floating processing unit (FPU) connected to the CPU [8826372]. CPUs are widely used in Space due to large Space heritage and also ease of programming and use. Several AI inferences engines are available for

CPU+FPU setups. The work presented here will show the results of extensive research in building a new AI inference that both reduces power consumption and also increases data throughput.

Parallel Processing Applied To Artificial Intelligence Inference

Within the field of inference engines for CPU+FPU, the focus for performance optimisation has been on matrix multiplication parallelisation [11], [12]. This process consists in splitting the operations required for a matrix multiplication into smaller to be executed by several threads in parallel. Figure 5 shows an example of this type of process, where rows from the left-hand matrix and columns from the right-hand matrix are individual operations to be executed by different threads.

Figure 5: Parallel matrix multiplication

Data Pipelining

The theoretical advantage of the above approach is its minimal latency [11]. However, there is an emerging alternative approach to parallelisation, which is based in the concept of pipelines [13]. This approach works in a similar manner to an assembly line, where each part of this line corresponds to a complete matrix multiplication. This approach is particularly well suited for AI deep neural networks (DNN). Figure 6 shows this approach. The main advantage make pipeline a reliable approach to data processing in resources constraint environment, like Space on-board computers, is its higher throughput: pipelining can enable a substantial increase in throughput with respect to traditional parallelisation [14].

Figure 6: Pipelining vs parallelisation

THE NOVEL THREADING MODEL

Klepsydra AI implements an innovative approach to pipelining for AI inference using lock-free algorithms [15] [16]. The layers in a deep neural network are assigned to different CPU cores via lock-free event loops to decouple the computations performed in AI inference. However, in addition to this, Klepsydra AI also uses traditional parallelisation to optimise the matrix multiplication operations.

This novel threading model approach can process data at 2 to 8 times increased data rate, while at the same time reduce power consumption up to 75%. This model consists of three main elements:

Figure 7: Novel proposed pipelining approach

- Use of lock-free ring-buffers to connect the matrix multiplications operations.
- Use of FPU vectorisation to accelerate the matrix multiplications
- One ring-buffer per thread, meaning that each matrix multiplication happens in one thread.

This novel approach can be seen in figure 7.

The parallelisation and pipelining methods are orthogonal to each other and but can also compete for resources. To prevent these two methods from providing opposing constraints, Klepsydra provides a 2-D threading model of the CPU. In a multi-core, multi-threaded system, Klepsydra AI can provide fine-grained control on which (and how many) CPU cores are used for pipelining and which are used for parallelisation.

Parallelisation improves latency at the cost of CPU usage while pipelining can improve throughput at the cost of latency. As a result, the balance between parallelisation and pipelining must be chosen depending on the constraints of the target application. The performance of Klepsydra AI in terms of CPU usage, throughput, latency and RAM usage for a particular deep neural network depends on the configuration chosen and can offer a wider range of applicability compared to standard inference engines like TensorFlow with TFLite.

Asynchronous Operation

Klepsydra AI is asynchronous by nature and this allows us to start inference on the "next" input before the prediction results of the previous input are obtained. Due to the pipelined architecture, the event loops processing the layers at the start of the neural network are free to process the next data even if the complete prediction is not available. For the purposes of benchmarking, we can thus set the frequency at which new images are fed to the system and calculate the latency as the time required for the result to be obtained. The throughput in this case is frequency at which images are fed to the system. The maximum throughput that we can use depends on the configuration chosen for balancing the pipelining and parallelisation tasks on the available CPU cores.

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

We compared the performance of Klepsydra AI running inference on the equivalent network with a TFLite version of the equivalent network on 3 different machines - a 2 core Intel Xeon E5-2686 (2300 MHz).

The equivalent network was generated using TensorFlow 2.9.1 [17] and exported to the TensorFlow Lite format, which is optimised for inference tasks. Klepsydra AI uses the ONNX format [18] to load neural networks and for this case, the ONNX version of the network was generated from the TensorFlow Lite version using the ONNX Opset version 12. This ensured that both the networks have the same characteristics. As an additional check, we also verified that both versions give the same inference results when the same random data is input to each network.

Both Klepsydra AI and TensorFlow were compiled for the respective architectures with all optimisations enabled. Both libraries were set to perform inference in 32 bit floating point format. TensorFlow Lite is configured to run with number of threads equal to the number of cores available i.e in case of the dual core x86 it runs using 2 threads. For the process of performance benchmarking, we use the following methodology: A new image with random data is generated at different regular intervals and input to neural network. We measure the time taken to obtain the prediction result, along with the resource utilisation during the prediction. Latency is defined as the time taken from the instance the image is input to the neural network to the instance the prediction result is available. Throughput is defined as the rate at which new images are generated and input to the neural network. In case of Tensorflow, a new image cannot be processed unless the previous prediction is obtained - the latency and throughput are thus inversely related. In case of Klepsydra AI, since the prediction is performed asynchronously, a new image may be fed to the neural network before the prediction result of the

Table 2: Performance Statistics for compression. CPU usage represented as the ratio of CPU % and input publishing rate.

	CPU (% / Hz)	RAM (Mb)	Latency (ms)	Throughput (Hz)
x86: Klepsydra AI	98	570	909	0.96
x86: Klepsydra AI (RAM optimized)	112	205	1805	0.39
x86: Tensorflow Lite	170	240	1552	0.54

Table 3: Pipelining configuration for different constraints on dual core x86 machine

Constraint	Event Loop cores	Threads	Event Loop Pool size
CPU usage	2	2	1
RAM	1	1	0
Latency	2	2	1
Throughput	2	2	1

previous result is available. As a result, the latency and throughput when predicting with Klepsydra AI have to be calculated separately.

CPU usage in these tests depends on the rate at which new images are input to the inference engine. As a result, we normalise the CPU usage using the publishing rate to obtain a performance statistic that is coherent across different publishing rates. It has also been observed that publishing input images at high frequency can stress the system and negatively affect performance metrics. By testing Klepsydra AI at different publishing rates, we can obtain the best possible latency and also measure the performance metrics when the system is loaded at maximum capacity.

Table 2 lists the performance metrics observed under different configuration scenarios. Klepsydra AI allows for a number of configurations and each configuration can result in a different performance profile. We tested all possible configurations of Klepsydra AI's pipelining setup at different throughputs and list the best metrics under different constraints in Table 2.

When tested on 2 core x86 machines, Klepsydra AI allows us to compress image data with approximately 2x less CPU and 2x less latency as required by TensorFlow Lite. In case of applications where the hardware has limited memory available, the 2D threading model allows us to tune Klepsydra AI to use lower memory while also reducing the CPU usage. The latency and throughput in this case is slightly worse than TensorFlow Lite. The pipelining configurations for these cases are summarised in Table 3. In case of the x86 machines, the configurations that result in best CPU usage, best Latency and best Throughput are the same.

CURRENT BOTTLENECKS AND FUTURE WORK

The network chosen for this work was originally developed for testing on server without constraints relating to CPU usage, power requirements etc which are typically common when considering on-board applications. The compression network includes custom layers with code written in C++ for entropy encoding. The TensorFlow Lite library has layers optimised for low power and CPU usage; however the layers used in the compression network are custom written and do not have a TensorFlow Lite equivalent version. The custom written code also makes it a challenge to test the compression networks using different AI inference engines. To test the performance of the neural networks, we need to manually separate the entropy encoding stage.

As a result, we have had to test performance on functionally equivalent networks with the same network architecture as the network chosen for our tests but with dummy weights. The ideal test would be to test on the real network with trained weights. We also have to consider that the entropy encoding stage may incur processing costs that we have not measured. In the performance comparison detailed above, the entropy encoding stage was removed from both versions of the network to keep the comparison fair and accurate. However, for real world tests we must include the entropy encoding stage in our measurements.

REFERENCES

- [1] Noboru Sonehara, Mitsuo Kawato, Sei Miyake, and K. Nakane. "Image data compression using a neural network model". In: *International 1989 Joint Conference on Neural Networks* (1989), 35–41 vol.2.

- [2] Guoxia Yu, Tanya Vladimirova, and Martin N. Sweeting. “Image compression systems on board satellites”. In: *Acta Astronautica* 64.9 (2009), pp. 988–1005. ISSN: 0094-5765. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2008.12.006>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0094576508004062>.
- [3] Yibo Yang, Stephan Mandt, and Lucas Theis. *An Introduction to Neural Data Compression*. 2022. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.2202.06533. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.06533>.
- [4] Johannes Ballé, Valero Laparra, and Eero P. Simoncelli. “End-to-end Optimized Image Compression”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations*. 2017. URL: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=rJxdQ3jeg>.
- [5] Johannes Ballé, Sung Jin Hwang, and Eirikur Agustsson. *Learned Data Compression*. URL: https://www.tensorflow.org/tutorials/generative/data_compression.
- [6] Johannes Ballé, Sung Jin Hwang, and Eirikur Agustsson. *TensorFlow Compression: Learned Data Compression*. Version 2.9.1. 2022. URL: <http://github.com/tensorflow/compression>.
- [7] Johannes Ballé, David Minnen, Saurabh Singh, Sung Jin Hwang, and Nick Johnston. “Variational image compression with a scale hyperprior”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations*. 2018. URL: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=rkcQFMZRb>.
- [8] David Minnen and Saurabh Singh. *Channel-wise Autoregressive Entropy Models for Learned Image Compression*. 2020. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.2007.08739. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.08739>.
- [9] Johannes Ballé. *Efficient Nonlinear Transforms for Lossy Image Compression*. 2018. DOI: 10.48550/ARXIV.1802.00847. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.00847>.
- [10] Deniz Oktay, Johannes Ballé, Saurabh Singh, and Abhinav Shrivastava. “Model Compression by Entropy Penalized Reparameterization”. In: *CoRR* abs/1906.06624 (2019). arXiv: 1906.06624. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1906.06624>.
- [11] L. Dagum and R. Menon. “OpenMP: an industry standard API for shared-memory programming”. In: *IEEE Computational Science and Engineering* 5.1 (1998), pp. 46–55. DOI: 10.1109/99.660313.
- [12] Sunil Shukla et al. “A Scalable Multi-TeraOPS Core for AI Training and Inference”. In: *IEEE Solid-State Circuits Letters* 1.12 (2018), pp. 217–220. DOI: 10.1109/LSSC.2019.2902738.
- [13] Geoffrey Biggs, Noriaki Ando, and Tetsuo Kotoku. “Rapid data processing pipeline development using OpenRTM-aist”. In: *2011 IEEE/SICE International Symposium on System Integration (SII)*. 2011, pp. 312–317. DOI: 10.1109/SII.2011.6147466.
- [14] K. Sravani and Rathnamala Rao. “High throughput and high capacity asynchronous pipeline using hybrid logic”. In: *2017 International Conference on Innovations in Electronics, Signal Processing and Communication (IESC)*. 2017, pp. 11–15. DOI: 10.1109/IESPC.2017.8071856.
- [15] P. Ghiglino and M. Harshe. “A deterministic and high performance parallel data processing approach to increase guidance navigation and control robustness.” In: *2020 IAF SPACE SYSTEMS SYMPOSIUM (IAC)*. 2020. DOI: IAC-20,D1,3,9,x56505.
- [16] Pablo Ghiglino and Mandar Harshe. “A Low Power and High Performance Artificial Intelligence Approach To Increase Guidance Navigation And Control Robustness”. In: (2021).
- [17] Martín Abadi et al. *TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Systems*. Software available from tensorflow.org. 2015. URL: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>.
- [18] Junjie Bai, Fang Lu, Ke Zhang, et al. *ONNX: Open Neural Network Exchange*. <https://github.com/onnx/onnx>. 2019.